

NICE POINTS COLLECTION
Volume 1
(English Version)

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Ringkasan

- ❖ Collection of nice points is sourced from Sokhi Huda's various papers.
- ❖ This volume 1 presents 12 nice points.

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1 *Martin's Islamic Studies Approaches*

If Richard C. Martin was to talk about the condition of Islamic studies in Indonesia, perhaps he would declare in Gus Dur's style: "Just like that bother, I have five parts, seven approaches, and eleven data fields (formula 5-7-11). If it's still lacking, I'll get my good friend Charles J. Adams and others to contribute, but do not forget the Phenomenology approach to solve insider and outsider problems.

(Sokhi Huda, November 1, 2010)

2 The Contemporary Thought of Muhammad Shahrur

Muhammad Shahrur's works speak itself, that he is a daredevil who opposes the flow of conventions, deconstructs, and offers new recipes based on philosophical views, historical reconstruction approaches, and hermeneutic methods resulting in methodological innovations of Islamic law, although he has never been called an expert of *tafsir* and *fiqh*. The temperature of the controversy grew when Shahrur was known to be a self-taught background, Professor of Civil Engineering, and a dyer's boy in the Arab region.

(Sokhi Huda, November 1, 2010)

3 The Contemporary Thought of Amina Wadud

Amina Wadud is a contemporary thinker who shows a bold and demure figure, as well as a high level of controversy. She has broken down the walls of conventional paradigms that were firmly defended for the previous 14 centuries. This breakthrough was carried out by Wadud not only in the conceptual realm but also proven by her in the realm of praxis. The main project is the struggle of gender justice in the spectrum of the context of the universal values of the Qur'an about the justice, dignity, equality of rights, responsibility, and social equilibrium of humans.

(Sokhi Huda, July 7, 2011)

4 The Modern Thought of Muhammadiyah

In the age of a century Muhammadiyah is tested by historical criticism in the ideo-theological setting, sociological reality, political arena, and the challenge of ijtihad thoughts of its future generations. Its historical dialectics leaves an epistemological problem that paves the way for thought and cultural dialogues. The emergence of autocritic and intercriticism of Muhammadiyah, in the dynamics of the Islamic movements, becomes a serious necessity. Its intercriticism carries "ideological mystery" that becomes reality in the constellation of modern thought.

(Sokhi Huda, May 10, 2011)

5 Theology of *Mustad`afin* in Indonesia

Theology of *Mustad`afin*, as a new feature of theology of *al-Ma`un*, advanced in its turbulent arena with contemporary challenges; nationalism, local tradition, cultural development, organizational economic factors, political dynamics, and criticism of modern and contemporary scholarship. Its liberation project is demanded to emerge from the exclusive hegemony of Wahhabi-Salafi theology, so that it can be accepted significantly as a liberation movement in Indonesia. On this scale, the tradition of NU, which was once an easy target for theology of *al-Ma`un*, was in turn calculated as a partner for its praxis strategy to solve the contemporary problems of the Indonesian nation and state.

(Sokhi Huda, July 11, 2011)

6 The West and Islamic Fundamentalism

The West and Islam holds the status of key actors in the history of global civilization. The inter-contributive relations between them, with the remaining prejudice agenda, shifts to an increasingly inter-egoistic relationship pattern. Its current is fueled by the tragedy of 9/11, the product of the action of Islamic fundamentalism. As a measure of resistance and survival, the West produces a number of policies (political, economic, and military) that actually encourage the growth of Islamic fundamentalism. Competition to achieve superior position clarifies the face of ambition to strengthen the existence and struggle of identity. At its peak, inter-egoistic relations form the dialectic of the existence, ambition, and identity of the West and Islam.

(Sokhi Huda, June 13, 2011)

7 *Global Salafism*

Emotional tension is in fact unstoppable because of the urgency of historical criticism experienced by Muslims. Part of the global phenomenal effect is self-imposed proclamation of Islam as the best value, power and authority that the world must recognize. This fact provokes a new perspective on the uniqueness of Islamic radicalism which refers to the vocabulary of peculiar terms of Islam; Hanbalism, Wahhabism, Salafism, Islamist, Jihadism, and other cognate terms. On the scale of criticism, the nature of the global grace of Islam turns into a global threat; violence, terrorism, intolerance.

(Sokhi Huda, January 10, 2011)

8 Contemporary Terrorism in the Islamic World

Terrorism, as a part of the wholeness of history, plays a role of control over tyranny-domination and the role of ideological actualization. With an inherited historical heritage, it not only expresses momentarily but penetrates the skates of the historical periods, and with the emphasis of the problem solving of the contemporary era, acts of terrorism are required to provide a response. All profanic risks are drowned entirely into a completely substance of sense of the faith.

(Sokhi Huda, June 20, 2011)

9 Islam dan Politics

The principles of Islamic politics are: no permanent opponents, there are permanent comrades, and there are permanent purposes.

(Sokhi Huda, June 3, 1999)

10 Pragmatism of William James

Thanks to the breakthroughs of William James, the present generation of America succeeded in building a subjective and individualistic self-image and "garden" of morals; while religious and spiritual life becomes functional and dynamic.

(Sokhi Huda, December 19, 1999)

11 New Statement of Wittgenstein

Do not ever ask Wittgenstein what a word means, but how a word is used.

(Sokhi Huda, 19-12-1999)

12 Scientific Language Profile

A term in science is not just a word. It represents the truth about reality. Truth is not one's personal property but belongs to the truth itself. It is for this truth the scientific language obtains a universal mandate.

(Sokhi Huda, 25-06-2003)